

EVALUATION OF THE SLEEP HYGIENE INDEX AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY STATES OF THE ELDERLY LIVING IN NURSING HOMES

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Abstract

The aim: the sleep quality and physical performance play a vital role in older adults' well-being to maintain good overall health. Therefore, the parameters that have a role in sleep and physical capacity are crucial to achieve a healthy aging outcome. In this study, we aimed at comparing the quality of sleep and physical activity state of the elderly living in 5 nursing homes.

Methods: the 181 elderly individuals living in 5 nursing homes were included in this cross-sectional study. Physical activity, sleep hygiene index and demographics were analysed using SPSS 23.0.

Results: overall, 68.5 % of the participants were male, and 31.5 % were female. There was no significant correlation between the sleep hygiene scores and physical activity states ($p > 0.05$). Those who were divorced, those who were on at least one type of medication, those who smoked and those with poor perception of health had statistically significant difference in terms of the Sleep Hygiene Index ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: other than findings of the presented study that influence sleep and physical activity, the many other factors in different geographical areas or cultures could be a reason that is interrelated with sleep quality and physical performance of older adults. In this study, for primary care and family physicians to boost the sleep quality of the elderly, we recommend improving their health perception, quitting smoking, discontinuing unnecessary medications, and increasing their social interactions.

Keywords: aged, exercise, nursing homes, physical activity, sleep hygiene.

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1. Introduction

Sleep problem is one of the most common complaints of the elderly. Sleep disorders have been found to be strongly correlated with diseases or premature death. These disorders diminish lifespan and have a negative impact on life quality by causing somatic and psychological issues. Reduced sleep duration, waking up often during the night and increased duration of daytime sleeping are the frequently encountered pathological sleep patterns in the elderly [1–3]. Adequate, restful, and quality sleep is important for mental and physical health. Sleep hygiene is a form of behaviour and habit as well as a way of environmental therapy that is important to treat sleep disorders. Better sleep hygiene improves sleep quality and quantity. Sleep hygiene comprises creating a positive sleeping environment [4, 5]. Lee et al. (2015) reported that perception of life quality and sleep hygiene are positively correlated [6].

In cases of sleep disorders experienced by the elderly living an institutionalized life, common life and environmental conditions at the institution are believed to be the cause of poor sleep quality.

Factors such as institutions being medicalized spaces, noises caused in common spaces, lighting, sharing rooms with others and presence of people with various backgrounds all affect sleep. Institutional routines cause individuals to be sedentary. Reduced levels of social stimulus and communication affect sleep quality [7]. Presence of chronic diseases also has an impact on sleep quality. If the elderly living in these institutions are active both physically and socially, sleep problems decrease. In most patients, sleep disorders are neglected because they are considered natural owing to their age [8]. Less than one fifth of sleep disorders are noticed [9].

Being active and having a pleasurable social life are protective against sleep disorders [10]. Physical exercise programs that are generally cost efficient, suitable for most individuals and generally safe are complementary or alternative approaches that improve sleep quality and reduce the need for consuming sleeping pills. Pharmacological agents used in treating sleeping disorders also result in significant side effects such as falling and cognitive impairment. In many studies, non-medication treatment approaches such as sleep hygiene recommendations, cognitive behaviour therapies and physical activity have been proven to be effective [11]. It has been proven that physical activity improves sleep quality and reduces sleep disorders and has a positive effect on mortality and morbidity [11]. Daytime sleepiness and physical activity have been proven to be significantly correlated. Sleep quality in the elderly who are active physically is better than that in those who are sedentary [10, 11].

In studies on sleep hygiene, inadequate sleep quality accompanied by daytime sleepiness and impaired state of being awake is mostly associated with reduced sleep hygiene. Daytime sleepiness is a reason for low physical activity [11].

According to the study on the frequency of chronic diseases and risk factors in Turkey, 15.1 % of the individuals in the age group of 65–74 years are physically active at an adequate level, 24.7 % at a moderate level and 60.2 % at an inadequate level. In the same study, the physical activity level for those aged over 75 years is reported to be adequate in 10.8 % of them and inadequate in 70.6 % of them [12].

Regular physical activity has a positive effect both on mental and physical health as well as sleep hygiene. Regular physical activity significantly contributes to sustaining a life independently. Barriers preventing physical activity should be detected and resolved, and the elderly should be supported in this respect [13, 14].

This study aim was to evaluate the Sleep Hygiene Index and physical activity states of the elderly living in 5 nursing homes.

2. Materials and methods

Study design and sample

The Manisa is a city of Turkey which is located at the middle-west of country with 1.429.643 people. The people 65 and over living in Manisa make up 10.9 % of population with 12.3 % (*n*: 175 846) women and 9.5 % (*n*: 135 816) men according to the Turkey Statistical Institute 2018 data. The city population pay attention and value on their traditional and cultural family structure, so they tend to live in their own house with their family and relatives. The elderly living in nursing homes were included in this cross-sectional study. The inclusion criteria for the study were as following – not using an auxiliary equipment, orthosis or prosthesis; not having a history of operation, fracture or trauma in the last 6 months, not having a neurological disease, not having a diagnosed sleeping disease and volunteering for the study. The number of the elderly living in all the nursing homes was 284; 103 of these individuals were excluded from the study because they were disabled (physically or mentally) and not volunteer or because of other reasons. The total number of individuals included in the study was 181 (64 %).

Ethics statement

All the procedures in the study that involved participants were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki

declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. Ethic approval was gained from Ege University with a decision number of 19-5.2T/32 in 29.05.2019.

Declaration of patient consent

The authors certify that they have obtained all appropriate patient consent forms. In the form the patient(s) has/have given his/her/their consent for his/her/their images and other clinical information to be reported in the journal. The patients understand that their names and initials will not be published, and due efforts will be made to conceal their identity, but anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

Data Collection

The data were collected via face-to-face interview with the elderly. The data collection form comprised 3 parts. The first part aimed at identifying their sociodemographic characteristics and health perceptions. The second part included Rapid Assessment of Physical Activity (RAPA) to assess their physical activity states. Developed by Topolski et al. (2006), its Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Cekok et al. (2017) [15, 16]. The data obtained through RAPA 1 were classified in 3 groups as sedentary, slightly active, and active. With RAPA 2, extension and flexibility were assessed. The third part included the Sleep Hygiene Index and was developed by Mastin et al. (2006) [17]. Its Turkish validity and reliability study was conducted by Ozdemir et al. (2015) [18]. The survey comprises 13 questions and is scored on a 5-point Likert scale (none: 1, rarely: 2, sometimes: 3, frequently: 4, always: 5). The index investigates how often a participant exhibits sleeping behaviours indicative of sleep hygiene to question whether sleep hygiene is good in their lives. The scores that were obtained range from 13 to 65, and higher scores indicate that a participant has a worse state of sleep hygiene.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained as part of the research were analyzed using the SPSS Statistics 23.0 programme. Descriptive statistical methods such as numerical, percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to assess the data. To analyze the factors correlated with sleep hygiene scores, t-tests, linear regression, and ANOVA test were performed.

3. Results

In the study, 68.5 % (*n*: 124) of them were male and 31.5 % (*n*: 57) were female, whereas in terms of marital status, 11.6 % (*n*: 21) were married, 32.6 % (*n*: 59) were single, 44.2 % (*n*: 80) were widowed and 11.6 % (*n*: 21) were divorced 29.2 % (*n*: 53) of the participants were illiterate (participants that have not an educational background or cannot read), whereas 70.7 % (*n*: 128) were literate ((Primary school, Secondary school, High school, University and higher) in all group (**Table 1**).

In terms of educational background, 44.2 % were primary school graduates, 12.2 % were secondary school graduates, 8.3 % were high school graduates and 6.1 % were university graduates or had a higher degree. The percentage of those that living in rural area was 27.1, whereas that of those living in urban areas was 72.9 %; 76.2 % (*n*: 138) of the participants were living in state nursing homes, whereas 23.8 % (*n*: 43) were living in private nursing homes.

Overall, 54.4 % of the participants had chronic diseases, whereas 44.3 % of them did not have any chronic disease. Although 68 % of the elderly were taking at least one type of medication on a regular basis, 32 % of these individuals were not taking any medication.

On comparing participants in terms of their health perception, 50.8 % of them had a health perception of «good» quality, which was the majority, and 2.2 % of them had a health perception of a «very bad» quality, which was the minority; conversely, 13.8 % of participants had a health perception of «very good» quality.

In terms of physical activity, 73.5 % were found to be sedentary, 18.2 % slightly active and 8.3 % active.

Those who smoked accounted for 29.8 % of the participants, those who never smoked accounted for 47 % of them and those who quit smoking in the past accounted for 42 % of them.

Some of the parameters were analysed with linear regression analysis and demonstrated in **Table 2**.

Table 1
Characteristics of the Nursing Homes Residents who were included in the study

Parameters	Number	%
Sex		
Male	124	68.5
Female	57	31.5
Marital Status		
Married	21	11.6
Single	59	32.6
Widowed	80	44.2
Divorced	21	11.6
Educational Background		
Illiterate	53	29.2
Literate (Primary school, Secondary school, High school, University and higher)	128	70.7
Primary School	80	44.2
Secondary School	22	12.2
High School	15	8.3
University and Higher	11	6.1
Place of living		
Rural	49	27.1
Urban	134	72.9
Type of Nursing Home		
State	138	76.2
Private	43	23.8
Presence of Chronic Disease		
Yes	102	56.4
No	80	44.3
Presence of Regularly Used Medication		
Yes	123	68
No	58	32
Perception of Health		
Very Bad	4	2.2
Bad	29	16
Indecisive	31	17.1
Good	92	50.8
Very Good	25	13.8
BMI Classification (<i>n</i> : 181, kg/m ²)		
1 (BMI: < 18.5)	5	2.8
2 (BMI: 18.5–24.9)	83	45.9
3 (BMI: 25–29.9)	86	47.5
4 (BMI: > 30)	7	3.8
State of Physical Activity		
Sedentary	133	73.5
Slightly active	33	18.2
Active	15	8.3
Strength/Flexibility		
0	162	89.5
1	4	2.2
2	11	6.1
3	4	2.2
State of Smoking		
Yes	54	29.8
No	85	47
Smoked in the past	42	23.2

Table 2
Linear Regression Analysis

Parameters	B	Std. Error	Beta	P
(Constant)	24.819	4.538		.000
Body Mass Index	-.203	.940	-.016	.830
Flexibility	-.592	.825	-.054	.475
Sedentary	.452	.684	.050	.509
Gender	.103	1.160	.007	.929
Marital status	.905	.628	.108	.151
Smoking	-1.773	.732	-.182	.017
Health perception	-2.151	.533	-.299	.000
Regularly Used Medication	-3.671	1.631	-.240	.026
Chronic diseases	1.292	1.544	.090	.404

In terms of the distribution of sleep hygiene scores, there was not any statistically significant difference between the groups of female and male participants ($p > 0.05$, **Table 3**). There were statistically significant differences in terms of their marital status. Although those who were divorced had worse sleep hygiene scores ($p = 0.012$), there was no significant difference between the groups of married, single, and widowed participants ($p > 0.05$). There was no statistically significant correlation between sleep hygiene scores and the presence of chronic disease, physical activity state, strength/flexibility, body mass index, educational background, type of nursing home and location where they spent their lives (i.e., urban or rural), ($p > 0.05$). Those who were on medication on a regular basis, those who smoked and those who had a «very bad» health perception had a bad sleep hygiene score ($p = 0.013$, $p = 0.000$ and $p = 0.000$, respectively).

Table 3
Sleep hygiene Score Distribution by the Participants Characteristics

Characteristics	Mean score	Statistics
1	2	3
Sex		
Male	12.76±7.51	P > 0.05
Female	12.19±5.87	
Marital Status		
Married	11.66±5.57	F: 3.756
Single	11.77±7.50	P: 0.012
Widowed	12.18±6.00	
Divorced	17.28±9.03	
Educational Background		
Illiterate	13.04±8.52	P > 0.05
Literate	10.17±4.67	
Primary School	12.25±6.78	
Secondary School	15.59±8.35	
High School	13.00±5.76	
University and Higher	13.81±8.03	
Type of Nursing Home		
State	12.07±6.88	P > 0.05
Private	14.20±7.34	

Continuation of Table 3

1	2	3
Area of Living		
Rural	12.18±7.05	P > 0.05
Urban	12.73±7.04	
State of Smoking		
Yes	15.72±8.29	F: 10.015
No	10.50±5.67	P: 0.000
Smoked in the past	12.76±6.35	
Presence of Chronic Disease		
Yes	13.40±6.94	P > 0.05
No	11.53±7.04	
BMI		
Slim	15.20±8.04	P > 0.05
Normal	12.36±6.99	
Overweight	13.01±7.20	
Presence of Regularly Used Medication		
Yes	13.47±7.01	T: 2.504
No	10.70±6.74	P: 0.013
State of Physical Activity		
Sedentary	12.48±7.40	P > 0.05
Slightly active	13.66±6.42	
Active	12.51±5.76	
Strength/Flexibility		
Muscular strength	12.74±7.05	P > 0.05
Flexibility	13.50±9.32	
Both	9.45±4.36	
None	14.00±10.03	
Perception of Health		
Very Bad	26.00±5.71	F: 6.980
Bad	15.79±7.75	P: 0.000
Indecisive	12.67±6.73	
Good	11.16±6.04	
Very Good	11.84±7.12	
Total	12.58±7.03	

4. Discussion

In the present study, we evaluated sleep hygiene and physical activity state in the elderly living in the nursing homes and this will be of significance for the programs that will be conducted at nursing homes. Sedentary behaviour affects sleep hygiene and is affected by environmental and cultural factors [19].

In the present study, there was no significant correlation between sleep hygiene scores and the sex, age, education, and body mass index. Thichumpa et al. reported that female participants had more sleep disorders and concluded that ageing is not an effective factor [20]. In the study by Luo et al., there was a significant correlation between the female sex and low educational background and sleep quality [21]. In the present study, the divorced participants had the worst sleep hygiene. In a study in which the correlation between marital status and sleep disorders was investigated, similar results were reported [22].

Overall, 50.8 % of the elderly included in the present study reported their health perception as «good». As the health perception got worse, the Sleep Hygiene Index worsened according to the results of the present study. In a study by Dalmases et al., similar results were reported [23]. Ageing is accompanied by various chronic and complex morbidities and being on medication brings about adverse reactions in the elderly. Kumar et al. reported that polypharmacy and inappropriate use of medication posed a negative impact on some sleep components, thereby causing sleep disorders [24]. Similarly, in the present study, those who used medication on a regular basis were found to have significantly lower scores of the Sleep Hygiene Index. There is also an important reason such as physical inactivity which should be improved for a better sleep hygiene. Why we must value physical activities for elderly to improve sleep hygiene were discussed by many authors and results of some studies indicate that sleep hygiene is positively affected by physical activity [13, 14].

Study limitations. A limitation of the study is that it does not make a generalization of the overall elderly population. Moreover, the scales and forms were applied via one-to-one interviews, and information was gathered based on the answers provided by the participants. It provides an insight about the elderly living in such institutions. The elderly living in nursing homes are provided with services, such as food and accommodation, that meet their daily needs and other services that meet their medical needs and treatments, and these are intended to sort out their social problems, improve their social relations, make use of their time in the best way, and sustain their activities.

Prospects for further research. The current and unknown parameters that are related to sleep hygiene and physical activity should be determined in later studies for a better understanding of factors that are interconnected in elderly health.

5. Conclusion

The factors that have a negative impact on the sleep hygiene of the elderly living in the nursing homes are being divorced, smoking, bad health perception and continuous use of medication. It is necessary for primary care and family physicians to take measures to enhance physical activity, to help them quit smoking and to eliminate unnecessary use of medication as part of the programs that will be administered for the benefit of the elderly.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest.

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